

Social Processes and the Performance of Food and Beverage Manufacturing Firm in Enugu State

Authored by

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Abstract

The study evaluated the social processes and performance of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state. The specific objectives were to: examine the effect of gain commitment on the improved employee productivity and identify the effect of communication on the optimization of resources of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state. The area of the study was food and beverage firms in Enugu State. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 1238 selected staff of the study organisations. The adequate sample size of two hundred and ninety-three (293) using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error. Two hundred and fifty-seven (257) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 88 percent response rate. Data was presented and analyzed using Likert Scale and the hypotheses using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). The findings indicated Gain commitment had positive significance relationship with the improved employee productivity ($r = .424 < .983, p < .05$) and Communication had positive significance relationship with optimization of resources of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state ($r = .383 < .966, p < .05$). The study concluded that gain commitment and communication had positive relationship significance on the improved employee productivity and optimization of resources of food beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The study recommended among others that the management of organisations should instill in the minds of employees the importance of shared commitment. Commitment nurtures camaraderie, trust, and a sense of caring—the essential elements a team requires to sustain itself in the long run.

Keywords: Social Processes; Gain Commitment; Beverage Manufacturing Firm; Enugu State

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Introduction

Man is a social animal. It is hard for him to live in isolation. They constantly live in groups. As part of these groups, they behaviour in a certain manner. Social life is not possible without interactions or relationships. Social interaction is known as general process whereby two or more persons are in meaningful contact-as a result of which their behaviour is modified, however, slightly” (Ahmed, 2017). Social processes are characterized by social interactions. Social interactions are reciprocal relationships which not only influence the interacting individuals but also the quality of relationships. According to Gillin and Gillin, as quoted by Samiksha, (2023), “By social interaction we refer to social relations of all sorts in functions – dynamic social relations of all kinds – whether such relations exist between individual and individual, between group and group and group and individual, as the case may be”.

Man plays many functions within the society in which we live. As a result, he does many and varied social roles as per his nature, needs or wants and roles. While working on these social activities or social actions he draws into close contact with others and the environment. This contact or relationships with others changes the action of the individual into interaction. The behaviour of each person is affected by the behaviour of others. This interaction is the basis of social life. Interaction refers to an action done in response to another action (Mondal, 2023).

Society is based in interactions. Interaction is the rooted ingredient of social relationships. The various social processes are the forms of interaction. The process of interaction, contact, forming and breaking down of relationships continuously occurs in society. Behaviour system grow as a result of interaction. Interaction gives energy to social life. As members of society people have to act and behave in accordance with some specific manner. They are always engaged in some sort of actions and interactions in the society. When the actions of the individual or individuals are influenced by the actions of other individual or individuals in a society and he in turn is exposed to their action that is called social interaction (Mondal, 2023).

It is not easy to improve the employee productivity rate with simply one or two techniques. Increasing a company’s employee productivity rate is a continuous process of building better environments, good connections with the workers and understanding their concerns. What truly helps is building policies that encourage people to audit the work environment and build up employee motivation as a continuous method of improvement. Implementing the perfect productivity plan is not an easy task. However, it is very important. The current focus on employee productivity gives Human Resource managers a peculiar opportunity to create better good work environments, use more techniques and help teams or groups put out their best at work (Azmi, 2023). Based on this, the study on the effect of social processes on the performance of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state.

State of the Problem

Social processes are the ways in which individuals and groups interact, adjust and readjust and establish relationships and pattern of behaviour which are again modified through social interactions. These social processes work for the solidarity and benefit of society. These are also known conjunctive social processes: Socialization, cooperation, adaptation, accommodation, assimilation and acculturation. The various modes of interaction between individuals or groups including cooperation and conflict, social differentiation and integration, development, arrest and decay or the repetitive form of behaviour which are commonly found in social life. The social processes have a role in shaping the society, helping to adjust the parts and maintain the social system as a whole in one way or the other.

In organizations today, are faced with dissociative processes that separate individuals and groups and can hinder the development of society and manufacturing firms specially food and beverage firms. The less committed people there are the less effective they are in motivating others. If a whole group acts with determination and commitment, more numbers of people will surely pay attention to work. Because of poor gain commitment and communication in the

manufacturing firms, the workers are discouraged seriously and do not have the confidence or experience to go through the hard times and hold out for the rewards of success.

As a result of these issues will lead to poor employee productivity and optimization of resources of food and beverage manufacturing firms. Based on this, the study aimed at evaluating the effect of social processes on the performance of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the effect of social processes on the performance of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state. The specific objectives were to:

1. Examine the effect of gain commitment on the improved employee productivity of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state.
2. Identify the effect of communication on the optimization of resources of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state.

Research Questions

1. What is the effect of gain commitment on the improved employee productivity of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state?
2. What is the effect of Communication on the optimization of resources of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study:

1. Gain Commitment has no relationship significance with the improved employee productivity of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state
2. Communication has no relationship significance with optimization of resources of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state

Significance of the Study

The study will benefit the following stakeholders; companies, communities, employee, and researchers;

The study will help and encourage People cooperate at a higher level when they share commitment. The stuff a group needs to keep it going for the long run. If people are committed to an effort for a period of time, they will learn what they need to know to be more effective.

Scope of the Study

The study will examine the effect of social processes on the performance of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state. The study was carried out in some selected food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state. The study focused on gain commitment and Communication (as independent variables); while improved employee productivity and optimization of resources (as dependent variables). The time scope ranges from 2019 to 2023.

Review of the Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Social Processes

A social process is a change that is consistent within a society over time. Social processes are characterized by social interactions, which are social exchanges that occur between individuals and groups in society. There are three main types of social processes, such as cooperation, competition, and conflict (Study.com., 2022). Social processes refer to forms of social interaction that occur repeatedly. By social processes we mean those ways in which individuals and groups interact and establish social relationships. There are ways of forms of social interaction such as cooperation, conflict, competition and accommodation etc. According to Maclver, "Social process is the manner in which the relations of the members of a group, once brought together, acquire a distinctive character" (Priya, 2023).

Gain Commitment

Commitment is dedication to a specific firm or organisation, cause, or belief, and a willingness to get involved. A byproduct of effective delegation is involvement. There is no way that firms can make the transformational changes needed to get it to the next level of operational excellence without engaging the brain trust of everyone (Brechtler, 2023). Commitment means succeeding in influencing others to endorse and support you, the task or plan. Commitment is necessary if people are required to take on jobs that may not be simple, quick or without cost to their personal time or work schedules. When you are able to lead someone to the level of commitment, several values are attached. These include: reduced pressure to monitor progress toward goals or spend time fighting resistance, greater sustained effort, People tend to be more efficient, creative, resilient and focused toward your shared goals and Working relationships improve (HR.Com, 2023). People who are committed to firm or organization or effort surely believe that it is necessary, they show up, follow through, and stick with it. The more people who are committed to the firm or organization, the greater the effort or momentum they can generate to get the job done.

Communication

Effective communication is the building block of any organization because without effective communication, organizational performance tends to suffer. Communication is a very crucial and significant element in an organization which is necessary for creating collaboration within the work environment that has effects on organizational performance, decision making and productivity. Without effective communication, organizational performance tends to suffer. communication is a line function, a two-way sharing of information that demands the freedom and opportunity to ask questions, get answers and exchange ideas" (Mukelabai & Jackson, 2021). Communication in the workplace occurs through different modes. Clarity in communication and timely information about changes affecting work are meaningful to labour productivity. Also, to achieve the targeted productivity level, managers should confirm clarity or understand instructions, provide enough training to employees, make sure cooperation at work exists by providing incentives and finally, develop a good communication plan for timely information delivery on changes affecting work. For an organization to be successful, it should not only keep an open line of communication between managers, employees, stakeholders, and the community, it should also have a strategy in place to ensure communication is effective, consistent, and aligned with business objectives (Guthrie, 2019). It is necessary for managers and employees alike to understand the principles of communication, the potential barriers to communication, and the importance of communication satisfaction in the workplace as it ultimately would increase the overall communication satisfaction in the organisation and boost employee productivity (Kirti and Tunisha, 2016).

Performance

Performance is defined as the accomplishment of a given task measured against preset known standards of accuracy, completeness, cost, and speed. In a contract, performance is deemed to be the fulfillment of an obligation, in a manner that releases the performer from all liabilities under the contract (McNamara, 2018). It is the completion of a task with application of knowledge, skills and abilities. Performance is about the efficiency (accuracy, speed, completeness and cost) of carrying out a task with the display of knowledge, skills and abilities. Even though it is a complex phenomenon; as it means different things to different people at different intervals and in varying occasions; it is a management concept that can be applied in all situations of an organization with similar processes. Organizational performance has been based upon the idea that an organization is a voluntary association of productive assets, including human, physical, technological and capital resources, in order to achieve a common purpose (Barney, 2012).

Improved Employee Productivity

Employees will be more productive if they are put in a position to aim for achievable goals. Goal setting helps employees self-motivate and build confidence in their ability to succeed. Employee productivity, sometimes referred to as workforce productivity, is an assessment of the efficiency of a worker or group of workers. Employee productivity is the engine on which a business thrives. Put simply, it's a measure of how much work an employee delivers within a specific time frame. Productive employees focus on the right things at the right times. There's very little wasted effort, and the work they do creates the results you want (Ottawa, 2022). As such, employee productivity shouldn't be confused with labor productivity (workforce productivity), which is the overall economic output of a country or company per labor hour (Kojic, 2022). For a Business and Organization to run well, the most important thing is the performance of Employees. When the employee is satisfied or happy, it will automatically increase productivity, and this is exactly what an organization needs to grow its business. Every organization should make it a priority to look at how they can improve the individual's quality and productivity to achieve a significant level (Azmi, 2023).

Optimization of Resources

Resource optimization is a management practice or strategy to boost employee productivity, efficiency, and performance within a project-based organization. To achieve these goals, it comprises processes such as planning, forecasting, allocating, and scheduling available resources and utilizing them intelligently to meet the organization's objectives. Resources can be human, equipment, facilities, finance, etc. The ultimate goal of resource optimization is to leverage the employees' maximum potential to improve business profitability. Resource managers use different techniques to optimize the workforce and balance their schedules (Saviom, 2023). The purpose of resource optimization is to maximize productivity by reducing the costs of labour and other expenses. Resource optimization techniques can also help you improve performance and meet customer requirements better (Male, 2023). Projects require a pool of competencies and every person in the company brings a set of competencies at various levels. When we have a way to schedule those competencies into projects, we can truly unlock the potential of all the resources available (Intelligent Management INC. Canada, 2021).

Conceptual Framework of the Study

Fig 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

Theoretical Framework

Functionalist theory guided the study by Bronislaw Malinowski (1922)

Functionalist theory was developed during a time when mass media had great power to influence society. Many theorists argue that mass media, defined as media designed to reach the mass of the people, have lost some of this influence. In addition, the process of mass communication does not always involve linear, causal relationships, and this is especially evident since the introduction of new forms of communication that allow individuals to create their own channels and environments where they communicate and interact. Re-search conducted by the Pew Research Center in 2016 showed that about half of Americans under 50 often get news online, including from social media. These developments have generated a need to reconceptualize communication and the ways in which media content is produced and distributed.

Empirical Review

The Effect of Gain Commitment on the improved Employee Productivity

Akinyemi (2014), conducted a study on the influence of age, tenure and education on organizational commitment in a developing country context. Focusing on Nigeria's dynamic banking sector, participants' age, tenure and level of education were measured against the three components of organizational commitment – affective, continuance and normative – in selected commercial banks to determine their relationship. The sample consisted of 303 full-time managerial and non-managerial employees from eight commercial banks located in the Southwestern part of Nigeria. The study concludes that older, longer-tenured and more highly educated employees did not report a higher level of commitment than their younger, shorter-tenured and less educated counterparts with regard to affective, continuance and normative commitment. The practical implications of this result and direction for future research with regards to developing countries are discussed

Ahmed, et al. (2017), conducted a study on the Device-to-device (D2D) Communication was primarily introduced to achieve the fundamental goal of high data rates, ubiquitous coverage with low latency, energy efficiency and minimization of cost for per-information transmission. However, with the advent of new applications culminating from the plethora of different market segments, D2D communication is being foreseen as an integral part of the emerging fifth generation (5G) networks. Widespread use of D2D communication can result in numerous challenges namely, security, interference, access control, network mode selection and power allocation. In this paper, firstly, we provide an overview of D2D communication in cellular networks and secondly, an extensive review is presented relating to optimization approaches used for resource allocation in D2D paradigm. We classify the relevant work with respect to different optimization objectives being considered while formulating optimization problems. Some commonly used optimization formulations have been explained which makes this paper a foundation stone for

further research in the area. A classification of optimization problem types and the relevant solution algorithms are also presented. We also discuss some candidate technologies for future D2D communication paradigm. Comprehensive coverage of the subject in this paper serves as a first step towards further research relating to the area of resource allocation in D2D paradigm.

Pepple, Akinsowon, & Oyelere (2021) conducted a study on the conceptualization of employee commitment and turnover intention in the Nigerian public sector using a qualitative approach. Findings suggest that (i) employees expressed a lack of sense of ownership and attached meaning to commitment based on (self-help) benefit gained from their organization, and (ii) the lack of scrutiny and accountability in the public sector resulted in low employee turnover intention. The study is novel for developing a framework underscoring how context may affect the conceptualisation of employee commitment and turnover intention

Afolakemi & Adeyemi (2021), conducted a study on the level of job commitment and organizational commitment dimensions of public secondary school teachers in Oyo State, Nigeria. Descriptive research design was used to guide the study. The population consisted of eleven thousand, seven hundred and thirty-two (11,732) teachers in public secondary schools in Oyo state from which multi stage sampling procedure was used to obtain two thousand, seven hundred and twenty-six (2,276) respondents while descriptive statistics of simple percentage, mean, and frequency were used to analyze the data obtained for the study. Findings of the study revealed that job commitment of public secondary school teachers was low (weighted mean = 2.31), affective organizational commitment was moderate (weighted mean = 2.62), continuance organizational commitment was high (weighted mean = 3.24) and normative organizational commitment was low (weighted mean = 1.77). Low level of job commitment among public school teachers was not unconnected to turnover intention indices such as workload, promotional prospect and teacher autonomy. The study, therefore, it was recommended that all hands should be on deck in order to devise necessary measures to ensure that teachers are more committed to their jobs which can be accomplished through genuine inspiration, a strong leadership style, and creation of an empowering environment that fosters education and learning, and a strong cultural recognition of the teaching profession. Also, government should ensure adequate educational planning or create a framework to encourage teachers to develop affective organizational commitment. Such policies should also aim at reducing to the barest minimum continuance organizational commitment among public secondary teachers, which was discovered to be high in this study.

The effect of Communication on the Optimization of Resources

Jatav, Datar & Malviya (2021) conducted a study on the sharing of resources in D2D users and cellular users faces a problem of intracell interference. The optimization of interference and shared resources increases the efficiency of device-to-device communication. This paper proposed the multi-objective-based algorithm to optimize resources in sharing of D2D users and cellular users. The proposed algorithm uses the particle swarm optimization algorithm. The applied particle swarm intelligence defines dual constraints function for the resource allocation in shared environments. The optimization process reduces the transmit power of D2D users and cellular users and increases the efficiency of the communication mode. The proposed algorithm describes the way of communication in the dedicated system model of the D2D communication interface. The proposed algorithm reduces the inference links and enhances the quality of service for the communication system. The incorporation of particle swarm optimization algorithm maintains the equilibrium state in both users. The proposed algorithm simulates in MATLAB environments and estimates the standard parameters. The analysis of results indicates that the proposed algorithm is better than the existing algorithms of D2D communication.

Zhou, Ayegba, Ayegba, Ayegba, Jie (2021) conducted a study on the impact of dynamic capacities on the performance of food and beverage enterprises in Lagos, Nigeria. The following sub-variables (strategic decision-making capacity, product innovation capacity, strategic flexibility, competitive intensity, technological turbulence, and technological capability) were employed to represent the variable of dynamic capacity. Also, the following sub-variables (sales growth, enterprise survival, enterprise efficiency, and competitive advantage) were employed to represent the variable of enterprise performance. Primary data was used to achieve descriptive and inferential statistics, and the statistics is estimated by the PLS-SEM method which was calibrated on Lisrel 8.70 software. This study found that

product innovation, competitive intensity and technological turbulence, technological capability and competitive intensity, and strategic flexibility are critical sub-variables in determining the robustness of dynamic capacities, as they adequately improve increasing sales growth, survival, and sustenance of enterprise into the unforeseeable future, efficiency of enterprise, and competitive advantage of food and beverage manufacturing enterprises, respectively, particularly in this trying period that is evidenced with technological change and competition, among others.

Oyedokun & Ayon (2022) conducted a study on the effect of social disclosure on the financial performance of selected Nigerian food and beverage industries. Ex-post facto research is used in this study. The information was gathered from the annual reports of the selected food and beverage companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange from 2016 to 2020. The study used content analysis to approach social disclosure data and State to analyse the acquired data. As a result, a panel data regression technique was used. For the period under consideration, 2011-2020, there were negative but negligible connections between the various scores assessing social and environmental disclosures and the financial performance of food and beverage manufacturers listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. Given the foregoing, the study recommends that government regulatory authorities and policymakers utilize important theoretical guidance to promote the establishment of a standard reporting guideline for the process of creating a company's non-financial report, or better yet, encourage the process of creating standalone reports and developing standard information disclosure templates, encouraging organisations to disclose corporate environmental monetary information.

Bhat, Shrinidi & Sairam (2022) resource allocation in communication networks employs different algorithms to efficiently allocate several resources like time, bandwidth, so on as demanded by the user at the source requiring establishing communication with another user at the destination. The choice of a suitable resource allocation algorithm primarily influences the performance and capacity of a network, resource utilization. Since the resources are usually limited, effective utilization and allocation of resources becomes important. Optical network meets the requirements of applications requiring larger bandwidths in addition to numerous other merits. Wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) in optical networks is a technique that saves and hence provides higher bandwidths. The field of resource allocation is immensely growing and new algorithms are continuously evolving. Modifications of various optimization algorithms are being developed to provide a good, thereby optimal combination of route and wavelength. This paper presents an algorithm which is a modified version of genetic algorithm to allocate resources optimally. The proposed algorithm provides a solution to routing and wavelength assignment (RWA) problem in all optical WDM networks. The optimality of the path is decided on the basis of weights of links in the paths. The algorithm was simulated using MATLAB software. The simulation result shows a plot of blocking probability that is decreasing continuously and proves the algorithm to be good and comparable to the values obtained using genetic algorithm. It produces a good combination of route and wavelengths and hence proves to be an optimal solution for routing and wavelength assignment problem. This algorithm can be extended and further optimized for other communication networks.

Summary of Empirical Review and Gap in Review

The few studies done were carried outside social processes and the performance of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state and did not focus to best of my knowledge on the Gain commitment on the improved employee productivity and communication on the optimization of resources of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state. Most of the studies reviewed analysed their data through A purposeful sampling technique, Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential statistics, Purposive Sampling technique, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient, Multiple sampling technique, Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method, Simple linear regression and Z test while the present study made use of Pearson correlation coefficient (r) to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling this research gap by evaluating the social processes and the performance of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state.

Methodology

The area of the study comprised of four (4) selected food and beverage manufacturing firms in Enugu state. These firms were: Aqua Raphael investment Ltd, 9th mile, Nigeria brewery Ltd, 9th Mile, Juhel Nig. Ltd, 35 Nkwubor Road Emene Enugu and Bons West Africa Ltd, Km 2 Enugu/Onitsha Exp. Road, Trans-Ekulu. The choice of these firms was due to high number of staff, Capital base above 15 million naira. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 1238 selected staff of the study organisations. The adequate sample size of two hundred and ninety-three (293) using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error. Two hundred and fifty-seven (257) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 88 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.734 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score (3.0 and above agreed while below 3.0 disagreed) and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Z – test statistic tool.

Data Presentation and Analyses

Data Presentation

The relationship between gain commitment and the improved employee productivity of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state

Table 1: Responses on the relationship between gain commitment and the improved employee productivity of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	The workers that gain energy form their duties are more productive.	425 85 33.1	240 60 23.3	96 32 12.5	56 28 10.9	52 52 20.2	869 257 100%	3.38	1.529	Agree
2	Workers that gain commitment work better with others and ever willing to develop.	305 61 23.7	240 60 23.3	108 36 14.0	64 32 12.5	68 68 26.5	785 257 100%	3.05	1.564	Agree
3	A committed workers shop up to work on time and do the necessary and even more.	370 74 28.8	264 66 25.7	135 45 17.5	40 20 7.8	52 52 20.2	861 257 100%	3.35	1.477	Agree
4	The workers that feel connected to the organisation are more productive and dedicated to their work.	430 86 33.5	264 66 25.7	63 21 8.2	120 60 23.3	24 24 9.3	901 257 100%	3.51	1.398	Agree
5	Recognition and reward enhance employee productivity in the organisation.	370 74 28.8	264 66 25.7	135 45 17.5	88 44 17.1	28 28 10.9	885 257 100%	3.44	1.351	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.346	1.4638	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 1, 145 respondents out of 257 representing 56.4 percent agreed that the workers that gain energy form their duties are more productive with mean score 3.38 and standard deviation of 1.529. Workers that gain commitment work better with others and ever willing to develop 121 respondents representing 47.0 percent agreed with mean

score of 3.05 and standard deviation of 1.564. A committed workers shop up to work on time and do the necessary and even more 140 respondents representing 54.5 percent agreed with mean score of 3.35 and standard deviation of 1.477. The workers that feel connected to the organisation are more productive and dedicated to their work.152 respondents representing 59.2 percent agreed with mean score of 3.51 and 1.398. Recognition and reward enhance employee productivity in the organisation 140 respondents representing 54.5 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.44 and standard deviation 1.351.

The relationship between communication and optimization of resources of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu State

Table 2: Responses on the relationship between communication and the optimization of resources of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu State

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Current communication networks reduce resources allocation problem	325 65 25.3	432 108 42.0	84 28 10.9	88 44 17.1	12 12 4.7	941 257 100%	3.66	1.165	Agree
2	Current communication networks allocate network resources optimally and fairly among users.	285 57 22.2	432 108 42.0	12 4 1.6	96 48 18.7	40 40 15.6	865 257 100%	3.37	1.411	Agree
3	Resource allocation plays a vital rule in wireless communication.	285 57 22.2	448 112 43.6	72 24 9.3	112 56 21.8	8 8 3.1	925 257 100%	3.60	1.145	Agree
4	Share resources increase the efficiency or device to device communication.	168 44 19.1	264 88 34.2	63 7 23.3	102 60 18.7	24 60 4.7	621 257 100%	3.26	1.407	Agree
5	The efficient resources allocation mechanisms in the organisation maximize user satisfaction.	435 87 33.9	240 60 23.3	150 50 19.5	104 52 20.2	8 8 3.1	937 257 100%	3.65	1.226	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.508	1.2708	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 2, 173 respondents out of 257 representing 67.3 percent agreed that Current communication networks reduce resources allocation problem with mean score 3.66 and standard deviation of 1.165. Current communication networks allocate network resources optimally and fairly among users 165 respondents representing 64.2 percent agreed with mean score of 3.37 and standard deviation of 1.411. Resource allocation plays a vital rule in wireless communication 169 respondents representing 53.3 percent agreed with mean score of 3.60 and standard deviation of 1.145. Share resources increase the efficiency or device to device communication 134 respondents representing 53.3 percent agreed with mean score of 3.26 and 1.407. The efficient resources allocation mechanisms in the organisation maximize user satisfaction 147 respondents representing 57.2 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.65 and standard deviation 1.226.

Test of Hypotheses

Gain commitment has no relationship significance with the improved employee productivity of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state

Table 3: Pearson correlation of gain commitment has no relationship significance with the improved employee productivity of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state

		The workers that gain energy form their duties are more productive.	Workers that gain commitment work better with others and ever willing to develop.	A committed workers shop up to work on time and do the necessary and even more.	The workers that feel connected to the organisation are more productive and dedicated to their work.	Recognition and reward enhance employee productivity in the organisation
The workers that gain energy form their duties are more productive.	Pearson Correlation	1	.655**	.648**	.701**	.615**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	257	257	257	257	257
Workers that gain commitment work better with others and ever willing to develop.	Pearson Correlation	.655**	1	.605**	.424**	.591**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	257	257	257	257	257
A committed workers shop up to work on time and do the necessary and even more.	Pearson Correlation	.648**	.605**	1	.788**	.983**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	257	257	257	257	257
The workers that feel connected to the organisation are more productive and dedicated to their work.	Pearson Correlation	.701**	.424**	.788**	1	.770**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	257	257	257	257	257
Recognition and reward enhance employee productivity in the organisation.	Pearson Correlation	.615**	.591**	.983**	.770**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	257	257	257	257	257

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 showed the Pearson correlation matrix on gain commitment has no relationship significance with the improved employee productivity showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows .424 < .983. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that gain commitment had positive significance relationship with the improved employee productivity of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state ($r = .424 < .983$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .424 < .983, p < .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .424 < .983$) is greater than the table value of .000, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that gain commitment had positive significance relationship with the improved employee productivity of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state as reported in the probability value of ($r = .424 < .983, p < .05$).

Communication has no relationship significance with optimization of resources of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state

Table 4: Pearson correlation of communication has no relationship significance with optimization of resources of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state

		Current communication networks reduce resources allocation problem	Current communication networks allocate network resources optimally and fairly among users.	Resource allocation plays a vital rule in wireless communication	Share resources increase the efficiency or device to device communication.	The efficient resources allocation mechanisms in the organisation maximize user satisfaction.
Current communication networks reduce resources allocation problem	Pearson Correlation	1	.841**	.838**	.458**	.662**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	257	257	257	257	257
Current communication networks allocate network resources optimally and fairly among users.	Pearson Correlation	.841**	1	.966**	.621**	.576**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	257	257	257	257	257
Resource allocation plays a vital rule in wireless communication.	Pearson Correlation	.838**	.966**	1	.573**	.591**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	257	257	257	257	257
Share resources increase the efficiency or device to device communication.	Pearson Correlation	.458**	.621**	.573**	1	.383**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	257	257	257	257	257
The efficient resources allocation mechanisms in the organisation maximize user satisfaction.	Pearson Correlation	.662**	.576**	.591**	.383**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	257	257	257	257	257

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 showed the Pearson correlation matrix on **communication has no relationship significance with optimization of resources** showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows $.383 < .966$. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that **communication had positive significance relationship with optimization of resources of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state** ($r = .383 < .966$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .383 < .966, p < .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .383 < .966$) is greater than the table value of $.000$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that communication had positive significance relationship with optimization of resources of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state as reported in the probability value of ($r = .383 < .966, p < .05$).

Discussion of Findings

Gain commitment had positive significance relationship with the improved employee productivity of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu State

Hypotheses one showed that the computed ($r = .424 < .983$) is greater than the table value of $.000$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that gain commitment had positive significance relationship with the improved employee productivity of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state as reported in the probability value of ($r = .424 < .983, p < .05$). Commitment is dedication to a specific firm or organisation, cause, or belief, and a willingness to get involved. Commitment is necessary if people are required to take on jobs that may not be simple, quick or without cost to their personal time or work schedules. In line with this hypothesis, the findings of the study of Pepple, Akinsowon, & Oyelere (2021) conducted a study on the conceptualization of employee commitment and turnover intention in the Nigerian public sector using a qualitative approach. The study revealed that employees expressed a lack of sense of ownership and attached meaning to commitment based on (self-help) benefit gained from their organization, and (ii) the lack of scrutiny and accountability in the public sector resulted in low employee turnover intention. The study is novel for developing a framework underscoring how context may affect the conceptualisation of employee commitment and turnover intention

Communication had Positive significance Relationship with Optimization of Resources of Food and Beverage Manufacturing firm in Enugu State

Clarity in communication and timely information about changes affecting work are meaningful to labour productivity. It is necessary for managers and employees alike to understand the principles of communication, the potential barriers to communication, and the importance of communication satisfaction in the workplace as it ultimately would increase the overall communication satisfaction in the organisation and boost employee productivity. Resource allocation in communication networks employs different algorithms to efficiently allocate several resources like time, bandwidth, so on as demanded by the user at the source requiring establishing communication with another user at the destination. The choice of a suitable resource allocation algorithm primarily influences the performance and capacity of a network, resource utilization (Bhat, Shrinidi & Sairam, 2022). This is in line with the result of hypotheses two which shows that the computed ($r = .383 < .966$) is greater than the table value of $.000$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that communication had positive significance relationship with optimization of resources of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state as reported in the probability value of ($r = .383 < .966, p < .05$).

Summary of Findings

The following findings were made by the study:

- i. Gain commitment had positive significance relationship with the improved employee productivity of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state ($r = .424 < .983$, $p < .05$).
- ii. Communication had positive significance relationship with optimization of resources of food and beverage manufacturing firm in Enugu state ($r = .383 < .966$, $p < .05$).

Conclusion

The study concluded that gain commitment and communication had positive relationship significance on the improved employee productivity and optimization of resources of food beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State. Contact or relationships with others changes the action of the individual into interaction. The process of interaction, contact, forming and breaking down of relationships continuously occurs in society. The more people who are committed to the firm or organization, the greater the effort or momentum they can generate to get the job done. These social processes work for the solidarity and benefit of society.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made by the study

- i. The management should instill in the minds of employees the importance of shared commitment. Commitment nurtures camaraderie, trust, and a sense of caring—the essential elements a team requires to sustain itself in the long run.
- ii. For better team collaboration and cooperation, the organisations should improve Communication flow to enable and drive better results for individuals, teams, and organizations.

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